

**INVOLYUTSIYA XOSSASIGA EGA BO'LGAN CHIZIQLI
BO'LMAGAN FUNKSIYA QATNASHGAN BIRINCHI TARTIBLI BIR
DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMA HAQIDA**

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ANNOTATSIYA. Ushbu maqolada chiziqli bo'lmagan involyutsiyali funksiya qatnashgan birinchi tartibli oddiy differensial tenglama qaralgan. Ayrim muhim xususiy hollarda oshkor ko'rinishdagi yechimlar olingan. Umumiy hollarda ham tegishli oshkor ko'rinishdagi yechimlarni olish mumkinligi ko'rsatilgan. Bunda hisoblashlarning juda ham katta hajmliligi bois ularni ushbu maqolada keltirishning noqulayligi aytilgan.

KALIT SO'ZLAR. Involyutsiyali tenglama, umumiy yechim, xususiy yechim, chet yechimlar, yechimni tekshirish.

KIRISH

Agar biror $f(x)$ funksiya biror X to'plamda $f(f(x)) = x$ shartni qanoatlantirsa, u holda u mazkur to'plamda involyutsiya xossasiga ega bo'lgan funksiya (akslantirish) deyiladi. Agar differensial tenglamada noma'lum funksiya yoki uning hosilalari involyutsiya xossasiga ega bo'lgan funksiyalarga bog'liq bo'lsa, u holda mazkur tenglama involyutsiya xossasiga ega bo'lgan differensial tenglama deyiladi.

Masalan, $f(x) = -x$ funksiya involyutsiya xossasiga ega bo'lgan chiziqli funksiya bo'ladi [1,2]. Haqiqatan, $f(f(x)) = -f(x) = -(-x) = x$. $f(x) = \frac{1}{x}$ funksiya esa involyutsiya xossasiga ega bo'lgan kasr chiziqli funksiya bo'ladi [3-7]. Haqiqatan, $f(f(x)) = \frac{1}{f(x)} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{x}} = x$.

$f(x) = \sqrt{1-x^2}$ funksiya involyutsiya xossasiga ega bo'lgan chiziqli bo'lmagan funksiya bo'ladi. Haqiqatan, berilgan funksiya irratsional funksiya hamda $f(f(x)) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-f^2(x)}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-(1-x^2)}} = x$. Shuning uchun ta'rifga ko'ra $y'(x) = \frac{1}{y(\sqrt{1-x^2})}$ tenglama ham involyutsiya xossasiga ega bo'lgan differensial tenglama bo'ladi.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI

Bunday tenglamalar va ularni yechish usullari ilk marta [1-3] adabiyotlarda keltirilgan. Bulardan tashqari bunday tenglamalarni yechishga bag'ishlangan ishlar yurtimizda G'.Mo'minov ishlarida ham uchraydi. Ushbu maqola ham aynan yuqorida keltirilgan involyutsiya xossasiga ega bo'lgan ikkinchi tartibli differensial tenglamaning oshkor yechimini topishga bag'ishlangan.

NATIJALAR

Teorema: Ushbu

$$y'(x) = \frac{1}{y(\sqrt{1-x^2})} \quad (1)$$

tenglamaning quyidagi oshkor ko'rinishlardagi xususiy yechimlari mavjud:

$$y(x) = \pm e^{\frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{\pi k}{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1+x} + \sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt[4]{2}} e^{-\arctg \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}}, k \in \mathbb{Z};$$

$$y(x) = \pm e^{\frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{\pi k}{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-x} - \sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt[4]{2}} e^{-\arctg \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}}, k \in \mathbb{Z};$$

$$y(x) = \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sqrt{2}+1}} \cdot e^{\frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{\pi k}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{2}+1}{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-x} + (\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot e^{-\arctg \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x} + (\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}}, k \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

Isbot: (1) tenlamada $x \sim \sqrt{1-x^2}$ almashtirish qilamiz. Natijada (1) ga teng kuchli

$$y'(\sqrt{1-x^2}) = \frac{1}{y(x)}$$

(2)

tenglamani hosil qilamiz. Buni (1) ning aslida

$$y'(t)|_{t=x} = \frac{1}{y(t)|_{t=\sqrt{1-x^2}}}$$

ekanidan va unda qayerda x kelgan bo'lsa o'sha yerga unung o'rniga $\sqrt{1-x^2}$ qo'yilayotganidan payqash mumkin.

Endi (1) ni quyidagi

$$y'(x)y(\sqrt{1-x^2}) = 1$$

(3)

ko'rinishga keltirib, so'ng uni yana x bo'yicha differensiallaymiz:

$$y''(x)y(\sqrt{1-x^2}) + y'(x)y'(\sqrt{1-x^2})\frac{-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} = 0.$$

$y(\sqrt{1-x^2})$ va $y'(\sqrt{1-x^2})$ ni (1) va (2) dan topib, (3) ga qo'yamiz:

$$\frac{y''(x)}{y'(x)} + \frac{y'(x)}{y(x)}\frac{-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} = 0.$$

Buni $yy' \neq 0$ deb ko'paytirsak,

$$y(x)y''(x) + (y'(x))^2\frac{-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} = 0,$$

yoki qisqacha

$$yy'' + y'^2\frac{-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} = 0$$

ikkinchi tartibli bir jinsli oddiy differensial tenglama hosil bo'ladi. $y' = z(x)y$ almashtirish yordamida unung tartibini pasaytiramiz:

$$y' = zy, y'' = z'y + y'z = z'y + zyz = (z' + z^2)y,$$

$$(z' + z^2)y^2 + (zy)^2\frac{-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} = 0,$$

$$z' = \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} - 1\right)z^2.$$

Uni integrallab z ni topamiz

$$z = \frac{1}{x + \sqrt{1-x^2} + C_1}.$$

Buni $y' = zy$ almashtirishga qo'yamiz:

$$\frac{y'}{y} = \frac{1}{x + \sqrt{1-x^2} + C_1}.$$

Bundan $\ln|y| = \int \frac{dx}{x + \sqrt{1-x^2} + C_1} + \ln|C_2|$ yoki

$$y = C_2 e^{\int \frac{dx}{x + \sqrt{1-x^2} + C_1}} .$$

(4)

Endi $\int \frac{dx}{x + \sqrt{1-x^2} + C_1}$ ni hisoblaymiz. Buning uchun Eyler almashtirishlarini bajaramiz:

$$\sqrt{1-x^2} = (1+x)t, (1-x)(1+x) = (1+x)^2 t^2, (1-x) = (1+x)t^2,$$

$$x = \frac{1-t^2}{1+t^2},$$

$$\begin{aligned} dx &= \frac{-4t}{(1+t^2)^2} dt. \quad x + \sqrt{1-x^2} + C_1 = x + (1+x)t + C_1 = x(1+t) + t + C_1 = \\ &= \frac{1-t^2}{1+t^2} (1+t) + t + C_1 = \frac{(C_1-1)t^2 + 2t + (C_1+1)}{1+t^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Natijada,

$$\int \frac{dx}{x + \sqrt{1-x^2} + C_1} = \int \frac{-4tdt}{(1+t^2)((C_1-1)t^2 + 2t + (C_1+1))}$$

(5)

kasr-ratsional ko'rinishdagi integralni hosil qilamiz.

Soddalik uchun dastlab $C_1 = 1$ bo'lgan holni qaraylik, bunda (5)

$$\int \frac{dx}{x + \sqrt{1-x^2} + 1} = \int \frac{-2tdt}{(1+t^2)(t+1)}$$

(6)

bo'ladi. (6) ni noma'lum koeffitsentlar usuli bilan sodda kasrlarga ajratamiz:

$$\frac{-2tdt}{(1+t^2)(t+1)} = \frac{At+B}{1+t^2} + \frac{D}{t+1}, (A+D)t^2 + (A+B)t + B + D \equiv -2t,$$

$$\begin{cases} A + D = 0, \\ A + B = -2, \\ B + D = 0. \end{cases} \Rightarrow A = B = -1, D = 1.$$

Bundan

$$\begin{aligned} \int \frac{-2tdt}{(1+t^2)(t+1)} &= - \int \frac{tdt}{1+t^2} - \int \frac{dt}{1+t^2} - \int \frac{dt}{t+1} = -\frac{1}{2} \ln(1+t^2) - \\ &- \operatorname{arctg} t + \ln(t+1) = \ln \frac{t+1}{\sqrt{1+t^2}} - \operatorname{arctg} t + \ln|C_2| \end{aligned}$$

topamiz. $t = \sqrt{\frac{1-x}{1+x}}$ almashtirishni e'tiborga olib hamda tegishli shakl almashtirishlarni qilsak

$$\int \frac{dx}{x+\sqrt{1-x^2}+1} = \ln \frac{\sqrt{1+x}+\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{2}} - \operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} + \ln|C_2|$$

hosil bo'ladi. Topilgan integralni (4) ga qo'yib, $C_1 = 1$ bo'lgan hol uchun berilgan tenglamaning yechimini topamiz:

$$y(x) = C_2 \frac{\sqrt{1+x}+\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{2}} e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}}. \quad (7)$$

Albatta, topilgan yechim C_2 integrallsh o'zgarimasining hamma qiymatida ham yechim bo'lavermaydi. Sababi biz differensial tenglamani yana differensiallash orqali yechdik. Xuddi algebrada berilgan tenglamani darajaga ko'tarish yo'li bilan yechganimizda chet ildizlar paydo bo'lib qolgani kabi, bu yerda ham chet yechimlar paydo bo'lib qoladi. Aynan C_2 ning qanday qiymatlarida (7) yechim bo'lishini aniqlash uchun uni berilgan tenglamaga olib borib qo'yamiz. Buning uchun avval (7) dan hosila olamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} y'(x) &= C_2 \left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1+x}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x}} - \frac{\sqrt{1+x}+\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{1+\frac{(1-x)^2}{1-x^2}} \cdot \left(\frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \right)' \right) e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} = \\ &= C_2 \left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1+x}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x}} - \frac{\sqrt{1+x}+\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{1+\frac{1-x}{1+x}} \cdot \left(\frac{\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{1+x}} \right)' \right) e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} = \\ &= C_2 \left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1+x}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x}} + \frac{\sqrt{1+x}+\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{1+x+1-x}{2\sqrt{1-x^2}} \right) e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} = \\ &= C_2 \left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1+x}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x}} + \frac{\sqrt{1+x}+\sqrt{1-x}}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x^2}} \right) e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} = \\ &= C_2 \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}}. \end{aligned}$$

Demak,

$$y'(x) = C_2 \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}}. \quad (8)$$

Endi (7) da $x \sim \sqrt{1-x^2}$ almashtirish qilamiz. Natijada

$$y(\sqrt{1-x^2}) = C_2 \frac{\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}} + \sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{2}} e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}}.$$

(9)

(8) va (9) ni (3) ga qo'yamiz:

$$y'(x)y(\sqrt{1-x^2}) = C_2^2 \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}} + \sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}}.$$

Dastlab $\Delta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}} + \sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{2}}$ ko'paytmani soddalashtiramiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot \frac{2\sqrt{1-x^2}}{\sqrt{2}(\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}} - \sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}})} = \frac{\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}} - \sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}} = \\ &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}} - \sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}}\right)^2} = \sqrt{\frac{1-x}{1+\sqrt{1-x^2} - 2\sqrt{(1+\sqrt{1-x^2})(1-\sqrt{1-x^2})} + 1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}} = \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{1-x}{2-2x}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Endi $\delta = e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}}$ ko'paytmani soddalashtiramiz:

$$\delta = e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}} = e^{-\left(\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} + \operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}\right)}.$$

$\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} + \operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x} = p$ deb belgilasak, u holda

$$\operatorname{tg} p = \operatorname{tg} \left(\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} + \operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x} \right) = \frac{\frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} + \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}}{1 - \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}} = \frac{\frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} + \frac{x}{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{1 - \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot \frac{x}{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1) \text{ surati: } & \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} + \frac{x}{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}} = \frac{(1-x)(1+\sqrt{1-x^2}) + x\sqrt{1-x^2}}{\sqrt{1-x^2}(1+\sqrt{1-x^2})} = \\ &= \frac{1+\sqrt{1-x^2} - x - x\sqrt{1-x^2} + x\sqrt{1-x^2}}{\sqrt{1-x^2}(1+\sqrt{1-x^2})} = \frac{1+\sqrt{1-x^2} - x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}(1+\sqrt{1-x^2})}, \end{aligned}$$

$$2) \text{ maxraji: } 1 - \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot \frac{x}{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}} = \frac{\sqrt{1-x^2}(1+\sqrt{1-x^2}) - (1-x)x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}(1+\sqrt{1-x^2})} =$$

$$= \frac{\sqrt{1-x^2} + 1 - x^2 - x + x^2}{\sqrt{1-x^2}(1+\sqrt{1-x^2})} = \frac{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}(1+\sqrt{1-x^2})}.$$

Bulardan $\operatorname{tg} p = 1$ va $p = \frac{\pi}{4} + \pi k, k \in \mathbb{Z}$ bo'lib, $\delta = e^{-\left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \pi k\right)}$ ni topamiz.

Natijada

$$y'(x)y(\sqrt{1-x^2}) = C_2^2 \cdot \Delta \cdot \delta \text{ bo'lib, ravshanki, } C_2^2 \cdot \Delta \cdot \delta = 1 \text{ bo'lsagina (7)}$$

funksiya berilgan tenglamaning yechimi bo'ladi: $C_2^2 \cdot \Delta \cdot \delta = 1$. Ushbu shartdan C_2

ning qiymatini aniqlab olamiz: $C_2 = \pm \sqrt[4]{2} e^{\frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{\pi k}{2}}, k \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Va nihoyat berilgan tenglamaning oshkor xususiy yechimini hosil qilamiz:

$$y(x) = \pm e^{\frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{\pi k}{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1+x} + \sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt[4]{2}} e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}}, k \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

2-hol. (5) da $C_1 = -1$ bo'lsin. U holda (5) quyidagicha ko'rinishga keladi:

$$\begin{aligned} \int \frac{dx}{x + \sqrt{1-x^2} - 1} &= \int \frac{-4tdt}{(1+t^2)(-2t^2+2t)} = \int \frac{2dt}{(1+t^2)(t-1)} = -\left(\int \frac{(1+t)dt}{1+t^2} - \int \frac{dt}{t-1}\right) = \\ &= -\int \frac{tdt}{1+t^2} + \int \frac{dt}{t-1} - \int \frac{dt}{1+t^2} = \ln \frac{t-1}{\sqrt{1+t^2}} - \operatorname{arctg} t + \ln|C_2|. \end{aligned}$$

$t = \sqrt{\frac{1-x}{1+x}}$ almashtirishni e'tiborga olib hamda tegishli shakl almashtirishlarni

qilsak

$$\int \frac{dx}{x + \sqrt{1-x^2} - 1} = \ln \frac{\sqrt{1-x} - \sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{2}} - \operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} + \ln|C_2|$$

hosil bo'ladi. Topilgan integralni (4) ga qo'yib, $C_1 = -1$ bo'lgan hol uchun berilgan tenglamaning yechimini topamiz:

$$y(x) = C_2 \frac{\sqrt{1-x} - \sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{2}} e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}}. \quad (10)$$

Bu yerda ham, topilgan yechim C_2 integrallash o'zgarimasining hamma qiymatida ham yechim bo'lavermaydi. Aynan C_2 ning qanday qiymatlarida (10) yechim bo'lishini aniqlash uchun uni berilgan tenglamaga olib borib qo'yamiz. Buning uchun avval (10) dan hosila olamiz:

$$y'(x) = C_2 \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1+x}} - \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{\sqrt{1-x}-\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{1+\frac{(1-x)^2}{1-x^2}} \cdot \left(\frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}\right)' \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} = \\
& = C_2 \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1+x}} - \frac{\sqrt{1-x}-\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{1+\frac{1-x}{1+x}} \cdot \left(\frac{\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{1+x}}\right)'\right) \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} = \\
& = C_2 \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1+x}} + \frac{\sqrt{1-x}-\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{1+x+1-x}{2\sqrt{1-x^2}}\right) \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} = \\
& = C_2 \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1+x}} + \frac{\sqrt{1-x}-\sqrt{1+x}}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x^2}}\right) \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} = \\
& = -C_2 \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Demak,

$$y'(x) = -C_2 \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}}.$$

(11)

Endi (10) da $x \sim \sqrt{1-x^2}$ almashtirish qilamiz. Natijada

$$y(\sqrt{1-x^2}) = C_2 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}-\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}}. \quad (12)$$

(11) va (12) ni (3) ga qo'yamiz:

$$\begin{aligned}
y'(x)y(\sqrt{1-x^2}) &= -C_2^2 \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}-\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot \\
&\cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Dastlab $\Delta = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}-\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{2}}$ ko'paytmani soddalashtiramiz:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta &= -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}-\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}+\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}} = \\
&= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}+\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}\right)^2} = \\
&= \sqrt{\frac{1+x}{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}+2\sqrt{(1+\sqrt{1-x^2})(1-\sqrt{1-x^2})}+1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}} = \sqrt{\frac{1+x}{2+2x}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}.
\end{aligned}$$

$\delta = e^{-\arctg \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\arctg \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}}$ ko'paytma uchun $\delta = e^{-\left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \pi k\right)}$ ni topganmiz.

Natijada

$y'(x)y(\sqrt{1-x^2}) = C_2^2 \cdot \Delta \cdot \delta = 1$ bo'lib, bundan yana $C_2 = \pm \sqrt[4]{2} e^{\frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{\pi k}{2}}$, $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ ni topamiz.

Va nihoyat berilgan tenglamaning yana bir oshkor xususiy yechimini hosil qilamiz:

$$y(x) = \pm e^{\frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{\pi k}{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-x} - \sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt[4]{2}} \cdot e^{-\arctg \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}}, k \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

3-hol. (5) da $(C_1 - 1)t^2 + 2t + (C_1 + 1)$ kvadrat uchhadning diskriminanti nolga teng bo'lsin: $d = 2 - C_1^2 = 0$. Bundan $C_1 = \pm \sqrt{2}$ bo'lib, biz $C_1 = \sqrt{2}$ bo'lgan holni qaraymiz.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{-4tdt}{(1+t^2)((C_1-1)t^2+2t+(C_1+1))} &= \frac{-4tdt}{(\sqrt{2}-1)(1+t^2)(t+\sqrt{2}+1)^2} = \frac{-4}{\sqrt{2}-1} \cdot \frac{t}{(1+t^2)(t+\sqrt{2}+1)^2} = \\ &= \frac{-4}{\sqrt{2}-1} \cdot \left(\frac{\sqrt{2}-1}{4} \cdot \frac{t+1}{1+t^2} - \frac{\sqrt{2}-1}{4} \cdot \frac{1}{t+\sqrt{2}+1} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4} \cdot \frac{1}{(t+\sqrt{2}+1)^2} \right) = -\frac{t+1}{1+t^2} + \frac{1}{t+\sqrt{2}+1} + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{2}-1} \cdot \\ &\cdot \frac{1}{(t+\sqrt{2}+1)^2} = -\frac{t}{1+t^2} - \frac{1}{1+t^2} + \frac{1}{t+\sqrt{2}+1} + (2+\sqrt{2}) \cdot \frac{1}{(t+\sqrt{2}+1)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Bundan

$$\begin{aligned} \int \frac{dx}{x+\sqrt{1-x^2}+\sqrt{2}} &= \int \frac{-4tdt}{(\sqrt{2}-1)(1+t^2)(t+\sqrt{2}+1)^2} = \ln \frac{t+\sqrt{2}+1}{\sqrt{1+t^2}} - \arctg t - \\ &- (2+\sqrt{2}) \frac{1}{t+\sqrt{2}+1} + \ln |C_2| = \\ &= \ln \frac{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{2}} - \arctg \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} - \frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}} \end{aligned}$$

kelib chiqadi. Topilgan integralni (4) ga qo'yib, $C_1 = \sqrt{2}$ bo'lgan hol uchun berilgan tenglamaning yechimini topamiz:

$$y(x) = C_2 \frac{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot e^{-\arctg \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}}.$$

(13)

Bu yerda ham, topilgan yechim C_2 integrallash o'zgarimasining hamma qiymatida ham yechim bo'lavermaydi. Aynan C_2 ning qanday qiymatlarida (13) yechim bo'lishini aniqlash uchun uni berilgan tenglamaga olib borib qo'yamiz. Buning uchun avval (13) dan hosila olamiz:

$$\begin{aligned}
 y'(x) &= C_2 \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x}} + \frac{\sqrt{2}+1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1+x}} - \frac{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{1+\frac{1-x}{1+x}} \cdot \left(\frac{\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{1+x}}\right)' + \right. \\
 &+ \left. \frac{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \left(-(2+\sqrt{2}) \right) \cdot \frac{\frac{1}{2\sqrt{1+x}} \cdot (\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}) - \sqrt{1+x} \cdot \left(\frac{-1}{2\sqrt{1-x}} + \frac{\sqrt{2}+1}{2\sqrt{1+x}}\right)}{(\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x})^2} \right) \cdot \\
 &\cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}} = \\
 &= C_2 \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x}} + \frac{\sqrt{2}+1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1+x}} + \frac{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{2\sqrt{1-x^2}} - \right. \\
 &- \left. (2+\sqrt{2}) \cdot \frac{\frac{\sqrt{1-x}}{2\sqrt{1+x}} + \frac{\sqrt{1+x}}{2\sqrt{1-x}}}{\sqrt{2} \cdot (\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x})} \right) \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}} = \\
 &= C_2 \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x}} + \frac{\sqrt{2}+1}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1+x}} + \frac{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{2\sqrt{1-x^2}} - \right. \\
 &- \left. \frac{2+\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{2} \cdot (\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}) \cdot \sqrt{1-x^2}} \right) \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}} = \\
 &= C_2 \cdot \left(\frac{\sqrt{2} \cdot \sqrt{1+x} + (\sqrt{2}+2)\sqrt{1-x}}{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{1-x^2}} - \frac{2+\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{2} \cdot (\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}) \cdot \sqrt{1-x^2}} \right) \cdot \\
 &\cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}} = \\
 &= C_2 \cdot \left(\frac{(\sqrt{1+x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1-x})}{2\sqrt{1-x^2}} - \frac{2+\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{2} \cdot (\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}) \cdot \sqrt{1-x^2}} \right) \cdot \\
 &\cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}} = \\
 &= C_2 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2} \cdot (\sqrt{1-x^2} + (\sqrt{2}+1)(1+x) + (\sqrt{2}+1)(1-x) + (\sqrt{2}+1)^2 \sqrt{1-x^2}) - 2 \cdot (2+\sqrt{2})}{2\sqrt{2} \cdot (\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}) \cdot \sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot \\
 &\cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}} = C_2 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2} \cdot (\sqrt{1-x^2} + 2(\sqrt{2}+1) + (\sqrt{2}+1)^2 \sqrt{1-x^2}) - 2 \cdot (2+\sqrt{2})}{2\sqrt{2} \cdot (\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}) \cdot \sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot \\
 &\cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}} = C_2 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2} \cdot ((4+2\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1-x^2} + 2(\sqrt{2}+1)) - 2 \cdot (2+\sqrt{2})}{2\sqrt{2} \cdot (\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}) \cdot \sqrt{1-x^2}} \cdot
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}} = C_2 \cdot \frac{2+\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}}$$

Demak,

$$y'(x) = C_2 \cdot \frac{2+\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}}$$

(14)

Endi (13) da $x \sim \sqrt{1-x^2}$ almashtirish qilamiz. Natijada

$$y(\sqrt{1-x^2}) = C_2 \frac{\sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}}$$

(15)

(14) va (15) ni (3) ga qo'yamiz:

$$y'(x)y(\sqrt{1-x^2}) = C_2^2 \cdot \frac{2+\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}}$$

Dastlab $\Delta = \frac{\sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}$ ko'paytmani soddalashtiramiz:

$$\Delta^2 = \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}+2(\sqrt{2}+1)x+(\sqrt{2}+1)^2(1+\sqrt{1-x^2})}{1-x+2(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1-x^2}+(\sqrt{2}+1)^2(1+x)} = \frac{4+2\sqrt{2}+(2+2\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1-x^2}+2(\sqrt{2}+1)x}{4+2\sqrt{2}+(2+2\sqrt{2})x+2(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1-x^2}} = 1.$$

$\delta = e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}{x}}$ ko'paytma uchun $\delta = e^{-\left(\frac{\pi}{4}+\pi k\right)}$ ni topganmiz.

Endi $\gamma = e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{1-\sqrt{1-x^2}}+(\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}$ ko'paytmani tekshiramiz.

Daraja ko'rsatkichlaridagi kasrlarning maxrajlarining tengligini bundan avval isbotlagan edik. Bundan

$y = e^{-(2+\sqrt{2}) \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1+x} + \sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{1-x} + (\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}}$ ni topamiz. So'ng $\frac{\sqrt{1+x} + \sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}}}{\sqrt{1-x} + (\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ ekanini

ko'rsatamiz. Haqiqatan

$$\sqrt{1+x} + \sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{1-x} + \frac{\sqrt{2}+1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{1+x},$$

$$\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x^2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{1-x} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{1+x},$$

$$1 + \sqrt{1-x^2} = \frac{1-x}{2} + \frac{2}{2}\sqrt{1-x^2} + \frac{1+x}{2},$$

$$0 = 0.$$

Bundan $\gamma = e^{-\frac{2+\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{2}}} = e^{-(\sqrt{2}+1)}$ ekanini topamiz. Natijada

$$y'(x)y(\sqrt{1-x^2}) = C_2^2 \cdot \frac{2+\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \Delta \cdot \delta \cdot \gamma \text{ bo'lib, bundan } C_2^2 \cdot \frac{2+\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \Delta \cdot \delta \cdot \gamma = 1$$

shartdan C_2 ni topamiz: $C_2 = \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sqrt{2}+1}} \cdot e^{\frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{\pi k}{2}} \cdot e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}+1}{2}}$, $k \in \mathbb{Z}$. Va nihoyat berilgan tenglamaning yana bir oshkor xususiy yechimini hosil qilamiz:

$$y(x) = \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sqrt{2}+1}} \cdot e^{\frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{\pi k}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{2}+1}{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1-x} + (\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot e^{-\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} - \frac{(2+\sqrt{2})\sqrt{1+x}}{\sqrt{1-x} + (\sqrt{2}+1)\sqrt{1+x}}}, k \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

Hisoblashlarning juda ham murakkabligi bois mumkin qadar ular batafsil yozildi.

Umuman, (5) da $(C_1 - 1)t^2 + 2t + (C_1 + 1)$ kvadrat uchhadning diskriminanti musbat va manfiy bo'lgan hollarni ixtiyoriy C_1 o'zgarmlar uchun ham qarab, berilgan tenglamaning umumiy yechimini hosil qilish mumkin. Biroq bu o'ta murakkab hisoblashlarni talab qiladi. Shuning uchun C_1 o'zgarmlarining yuqoridagilar kabi tayin qiymatlarida xususiy yechimlarni topish bilan cheklanamiz.

XULOSA

Ushbu maqolada biz chiziqli bo'lmagan involyutsiyali funksiya qatnashgan birinchi tartibli oddiy differensial tenglamaning oshkor ko'rinishdagi yechimlarini topdik. Bunda differensial tenglamani yana differensiallash usuli bilan yechdik. Biz

berilgan tenglamani yuqori tartibli bir jinsli oddiy differensial tenglamaga keltirib oldik, chet yechimlarni chiqarib tashlashni tushuntirdik va kerakli muhim natijalarni oldik.

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